

THE INSTRUMENTAL MUSIC AND ACCOMPANIMENT CLASSES, DEPARTMENT OF EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION IN BUCHEON UNIVERSITY UZBEKISTAN BRANCH IN TASHKENT

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Abstract. The purpose of this study is to present actual application cases of students according to the lecture plan of "Musical Instruments and Accompaniment Method" in the 2nd semester of 2023 of the Department of Early Childhood Education at the Uzbekistan Branch of Bucheon University and to find its implications.

In addition, Based on the two application results that is a curriculum comparison and applied it to the lecture derived by the Uzbek curriculum *Ilkadam* (competency in the creative development field) and the Korean early childhood education curriculum *Nuri Curriculum* (art experience area) and Secondly the results of the lecture based on their study of basic theory for instrumental, accompaniment method and their practices of melody accompaniment, rhythm ensemble, handbell performance, It was shown that these two applications were significantly meaningful for the students. They understood the basic theory well and participated well in the practice. Throughout the application results, Implications were presented.

Keywords: Instruments and accompaniment, piano accompaniment, chord notation, key names, rhythm ensemble, handbell

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi Puchon universitetining O'zbekistondagi filialida 2023-yilning 2-semestrda "Musiqiy asboblari va jo'r bo'lish usullari" fanidan o'tilgan darslarda talabalar tomonidan "Musiqiy asboblari va jo'r bo'lish usullari" fani uchun tuzilgan dars rejasiga muvofiq amalga oshirilgan amaliy misollarni ko'rsatish va ulardan kelib chiqadigan xulosalarni tahlil qilishdan iboratdir.

Shuningdek, O'zbekistonning "Ilk Qadam" (ijodiy rivojlanish yo'nalishi bo'yicha kompetensiya) ta'lim dasturi bilan Koreyaning "Nuri" ta'lim dasturi (san'at tajribasi yo'nalishi)ni solishtirish, darsga tadbiq qilingan misollarni tahlil qilish orqali talabalarning musiqiy asboblari va jo'r bo'lish usullari bo'yicha asosiy nazariy bilimlarni, musiqiy jo'rlik mashqlari, ritmik ansambllari, qo'l qo'ng'iroqlarini ijro etish orqali yaxshi tushunganliklari va amaliy mashg'ulotlarda faol ishtirok etganliklarini namoyish qilishdan iborat. Ushbu dars natijalari asosida xulosalar ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqiy asboblari va jo'r bo'lish usullari, pianino jo'r bo'lish usullari, akkord notasi, gamma nomlari, ritmik ansambl, qo'l qo'ng'iroqchalari.

Аннотация. Целью данного исследования является представление практических примеров применения студентами курса "Музыкальные инструменты и аккомпанемент" университета Пучон в Узбекистане, 2 семестра 2023 года, в соответствии с планом лекций, а также выявление сильных и слабых сторон.

Кроме того, в исследовании проводится сравнение узбекистанской учебной программы "Илкadam" (компетенции в области развития творчества) и корейской учебной программы для дошкольного образования "Нури" (область художественного опыта), а также рассматриваются примеры применения на лекциях. Студенты хорошо

усвоили базовые теоретические знания по музыкальным инструментам и аккомпанементу, активно участвовали в практических занятиях по аккомпанементу, ансамблевой игре и игре на колокольчиках. На основе результатов этого курса представлены выводы.

Ключевые слова: музыкальные инструменты и аккомпанемент, аккомпанемент на фортепиано, аккордовые ноты, названия нот, ансамблевая игра, колокольчики.

Early childhood music education has a positive effect on the development of young children. In particular, playing musical instruments in the art experience area of the Nuri curriculum is a good activity for learning musical concepts. (1) This musical instrument and accompaniment method (2) course was a 15-week course including theory and practice, and included Uzbek Ilkadam (3) and the Nuri curriculum (4), which is a Korean early childhood education curriculum. The goal of the national level musical instrument and accompaniment method (5) is to learn the basic theories necessary for musical instruments and accompaniment based on the national level curriculum, acquire learning content and teaching methods considering the development and interests of young children, plan musical activities for young children, and implement and evaluate them through practical exercises.

Research Question

What are some examples of practical applications of the theory required for the 1-1 accompaniment?

1-2 What are the examples of practical practice of melodic accompaniment in the classroom?

1-3 rhythmic accompaniment. What are the application cases of rhythm ensemble and handbell practice classes?

The subject of the study is 24 first-year Russian students and 13 Uzbek students from the Department of Early Childhood Education at Bucheon National University's Tashkent Campus. The instrumental music and accompaniment classes for first-year students were held for a total of 15 weeks, with 2 hours per week and 1 hour of theory followed by 1 hour of practical lessons. The teams consisted of 7 teams.

The research procedures and teaching and learning methods will be conducted from September to December 2023 for a total of 1

After understanding the Uzbekistan curriculum 'Ilkadam' and the Korean curriculum 'Nuri Course', you will learn the basic information of the two countries' curriculums. (6) Lee Hee-kyung (2019.p.233) was shared, and a lecture was given according to a detailed plan to be applied after comparing Ilgadam's competencies in the field of creative development and the areas of art experience in the Nuri process.

<Chart 1> **"Ijodiy rivojlanish" sohasi kompetensiyalari**

3.2.5. "Ijodiy rivojlanish" sohasi kompetensiyalari

"Ijodiy rivojlanish" sohasidagi 'ta'lim va tarbiya jarayoni yakuniga 6-7 yoshli bola:

- san'at va madaniyatga qiziqishni namoyon qiladi;
- milliy an'analarni qadrlaydi va ularni kundalik hayotining bir qismi sifatida idrok etadi;
- san'atning muayyan turini afzal ko'rishini mustaqil ravishda ifodalaydi;
- olingan bilim va ko'nikmalardan turli hayotiy vaziyatlarda o'z ijodiy rejalarini tuzish va tatbiq qilish uchun foydalanadi;

- insonning dunyoni o‘zgartirishdagi yaratuvchanlik rolini tushunadi.

‘Ilkadam’ (2022. P.19)

<Chart 2> Goals and contents of the Nuri Curriculum Art Experience Area

target	Have an interest in beauty and art and enjoy creative expression.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feel beauty in nature, life, and art • Enjoy the process of creative expression through art • Respect diverse artistic expressions 	
Content category	detail
Find beauty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feel and enjoy beauty in nature and life • Take an interest in artistic elements and explore them
Express yourself creatively	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I enjoy singing • Create simple sounds and rhythms with your body, objects, and instruments. • Express yourself freely through movement and dance using your body or tools • Express your thoughts and feelings using various art materials and tools.
Appreciating Art	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I enjoy imagining things when I see different types of art. • Respect different artistic expressions • Become interested in and familiar with our country’s traditional arts

2019 Revised Nuri Curriculum Commentary Ministry of Education, Ministry of Health and Welfare p92(7)

Studying title	Week (Hour)	Implementation criterion (detail)
Theory and practice required for accompaniment	1-2(4 hours)	Music theory required for accompaniment. Learning the main 3 chords, types, necessity, and details of melody accompaniment.
Practical practice of accompaniment	3~7(10 hours)	Practice the nursery rhymes in the major scale Chord practice. (4/4, 2/4 beat, 4/3 beat, 8/6 beat) Playing Doira, playing Glorocen Spiel Kyungmyeongchang by fixed method, Kyungmyeongchang by moving method
Accompaniment, rhythm ensemble, hand bell practical practice, practical evaluation	8-15 weeks (16 hours)	Archa bayram Gyeomyeongchang, rhythm ensemble, singing the national anthem in the key of G major, Gyeomyeongchang, accompaniment, playing handbells Archa bayram

Ensemble class details by week (Lee Hyun-sook, Lee Jeong-eun. 2020. p. 168)
(8) Reference

Results

1) Practice of the theory required for accompaniment

I understood well the Uzbek early childhood education curriculum, Ilkadam (competency in the creative development field) and Korea's 2019 revised Nuri curriculum (art experience field), and participated well in understanding the basic theories required for accompaniment, such as types of staff, clefs, pitch names, accidentals, notes and beats, musical terms, and performance techniques, and in being able to play with the correct posture.

2) Practical practice of accompaniment

Types, necessity, and posture of accompaniment, practice of children's songs in the major scale Types, necessity, and posture of accompaniment. Singing Hello, Matching the beat with the rhythm bar (Playing by looking at the Little Star score)

Types of accompaniment, practice of nursery rhymes in each major scale, chord practice. (4/4) Playing the Doira. Playing the Kodaison Giho, Glorocen Spiel, and playing the fixed-do method Gyeomyeongchang and the moving-do method Gyeomyeongchang were done well.

<Picture 1> Piano Playing Pictures

3) Accompaniment, rhythm ensemble, handbell practice and final evaluation (practical)

We practiced chord practice (2/4 beat, 4/3 beat, 8/6 beat), Archa bayram gye-myeong-chang, singing rhythm ensemble, singing G major (national anthem) with Gye-myeong-chang piano accompaniment, and playing handbells. The practice was divided into group and

individual evaluations. For the individual evaluation, we played the C major children's song Three Bears on the piano, and for the group evaluation, we played Archa bayram gye-myeong-chang, singing rhythm ensemble, and playing handbells to the Do-Re-Mi song by Sound of Music. We happily participated by matching the notes and beats well.

Conclusion

Based on the study problems, conclusions are suggested as below.

First, this study focuses on comparing Uzbekistan's 'Ilkadam' curriculum with Korea's 'Nuri' curriculum revised in 2019 to gain a deeper understanding, and understanding the basic theories of music for early childhood music education to apply instruments and accompaniment methods to children so that they can provide high-quality classes.

Second, through this learning process of understanding the basic theory of music and facing actual kindergarten classes, prospective teachers can prepare to become qualified teachers. The goal of the early childhood education theory lecture is to educate students not only about knowledge, but also about the difference between simple learning materials and actual classroom management through a deep understanding of the entire curriculum of 'Ilkadam' in Uzbekistan and 'Nuri' in Korea (7).

Third, through the practical use of the accompaniment, I learned the main 3 chords, sheet music, and key names, and learned how to play the children's piano with the correct posture. However, due to the lack of practice time, I mainly practiced the C major key, and I found that I did not have enough time to practice the F major and G major keys. Therefore, I suggest increasing the class time.

Fourth, while practicing the accompaniment to children's songs (Uzbek, Russian, Korean) as a practical class, Uzbek children's songs do not have an introduction or a postscript, and even music majors do not know their meaning, so they practiced by providing sheet music with a Korean children's song introduction and a postscript. Therefore, it is necessary to teach the introduction and postscript to Uzbek children's songs, and it is suggested that teacher training should be conducted accordingly.

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